

Improving take-over performance during cognitive distraction with an eye-gaze and situation adaptive human-machine interface

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Abstract: Automated driving (AD) (i.e., SAE level 3 AD) allows drivers to do something else, yet they can be required to takeover when the AD ends. We tested how an eye-gaze and situation adaptive human-machine interface (HMI) could improve take-over performance when drivers could be cognitively distracted by a conversation. We hypothesized that the eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI would improve the reconstruction of situation awareness (SA) (the fact of understanding a situation and being able to anticipate the next events) and thereby take-over performance. We conducted a driving simulator experiment with 42 participants (14 per HMI condition: control with a basic HMI, situation adaptive HMI, eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI) who drove on the highway with a SAE level 3 AD activated and experienced take-over requests. The eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI improved: (i) SA reconstruction since participants presented higher gaze dispersion, faster RT to the left mirror and spent more time looking at the left mirror, which indicated more visual searches and more information gathered during the take-overs; (ii) take-over performance and safety with increased time to collision and fewer collisions. Our HMI therefore exhibited promising results. Overall, adaptive HMIs seem to be a good option to ensure better take-over performance safety compared to non-adaptive HMIs.

1. Introduction

Driving automation provides the driver different level of support, from an automated driving (AD) assistance in a SAE level 2 to an AD feature in a SAE level 3 (SAE international, 2016). With higher levels of automation, the driver is progressively moved away from the driving loop, resulting in a decreased situation awareness (SA), namely, the fact of understanding a situation and being able to anticipate the next events (Endsley, 1995). Moreover, the AD can end leading the driver to takeover which requires quickly regaining the SA (Morales-Alvarez et al., 2020).

The period during which the driver regains SA are cognitively demanding (i.e., requiring cognitive and visual attention, see Gold et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2018) and can be impacted if the driver was distracted by a non-driving related task (NDRT), such as having a phone conversation (for a review, see Merlhiot & Bueno, 2021; Zhang et al., 2019).

As mentioned, SA reconstruction relies on visual search that depends on two independent visual attentional processes (e.g., Connor et al., 2004; Katsuki & Constantinidis, 2014; Pinto et al., 2013; Theeuwes, 2010). (i) A bottom-up process that arises from the salience of a stimuli, based on its characteristics in a visual scene. (ii) A top-down process that corresponds to the driver's attention to visual elements that can be guided by knowledge or feedback. These processes can be impacted by cognitive load (i.e., the amount of cognitive resource used), which reduces visual attention from top-down processes and, conversely, increases visual attention from bottom-up processes (Longstaffe et al., 2014). We thus considered assisting the reconstruction of SA by highlighting important visual elements (bottom-up effect) and provide feedback regarding the driver's visual search (top-down effect) by using an eye-gaze and situation adaptive human-machine interface (HMI).

We hypothesized that the eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI would improve the reconstruction of SA and

thereby take-over performance by supporting the two processes associated to a visual search as follow: (i) A bottom-up effect was achieved by using visual cues (i.e., with augmented reality) on important information to direct visual attention to relevant information for the SA reconstruction. (ii) A top-down effect was obtained by giving auditory feedback to focus attention on any important information related to the SA reconstruction that the driver may have missed.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

We obtained a sample of 42 participants (23 females, 19 males) with a mean age of 35.64 ± 9.78 years. All participants signed a written informed consent form and received 40 euros for their participation.

2.2 Driving simulator and eye-tracker

We used a medium-fidelity static driving simulator, which ran under SCANeR studio 2023.1 (Avsimulation®) with a synchronized eye-tracker (Smart Eye Pro 6.0) sampled at 60 Hz.

2.3 Experimental design

The study was conducted in a driving simulator with a car equipped with a SAE level 3 highway AD. During the AD, participants experienced take-over requests (TOR) which involved lane changes with ongoing traffic while being cognitively distracted by the twenty-questions task (TQT) (Merat et al., 2012), which simulates a conversation to get closer to ecological settings of AD.

We used the properties of the adaptive HMI as a between-subject variable to created three groups of participants (control with a basic HMI, situation adaptive HMI, eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI). Our design included the TOR time-budget as a within-subject variable:

urgent (i.e., TOR = 7 seconds) and planned TOR (i.e., TOR = 30 seconds).

2.3.1 TOR time-budget and use-cases:

We used 3 urgent and 2 planned TORs, all occurred on the highway at 130 km/h with the ego-vehicle in the right lane and with surrounding traffic. The first four TORs required a lane change due to an obstacle (i.e., stopped vehicle, work zone, lane reduction) and the last one required an emergency braking.

2.3.2 Eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI:

The situation adaptive part of the HMI highlighted important elements and used a 3-colors code based on TTC (Fig. 1): red (TTC < 2s); yellow (TTC = [2s,4s]); green (TTC > 4s). The eye-gaze adaptive part of the HMI corresponded to auditory feedback (e.g., check the rear mirror) that was emitted after a certain time (i.e., 2s after Urgent TOR, 10s after Planned TOR) if an area of interest (i.e., road, rear mirror, left mirror) was missed.

Fig. 1. Example of the situation adaptive HMI

2.4 Procedure

Participants started with a 15-minutes training session during which they familiarized with the driving simulator and experienced a TOR. After that, they completed the main scenario that lasted about 30 minutes.

2.5 Statistical analysis

All analysis were obtained from linear mixed models with the two independent variables as fixed factors and participants as random variable. Pairwise comparisons used Bonferroni corrections.

3. Results

3.1 Eye-gaze metrics

In the “Eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI” condition, participants exhibited higher gaze dispersion, $F(2,40.5) = 3.74, p = .011$, faster reaction time (RT) to the left mirror, $F(2,191) = 6.91, p < .001$, and higher percentage of time spent looking at the left mirror, $F(2,43.9) = 4.57, p = .016$, (Fig. 2).

We obtained an interaction effect between the HMI and TOR time-budget conditions for the percentage of participants who checked at least one mirror (i.e., left mirror, rear mirror) before performing an action (i.e., changing lane, braking), $F(2,154) = 3.51, p = .032$, (Fig. 3).

In the “Eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI” condition, participants received feedback to check the rear mirror 90% of the time, 95% CI [83%,97%], and to check the left mirror in 61% of the time, 95% CI [50%,73%]. After receiving feedback, participants checked within 3 seconds the rear mirror 15% of the time, 95% CI [3%,27%], and the left mirror 80% of the time, 95% CI [67%,93%], which was different from randomness, $F(1, 62) = 54.1, p < .001$, $F(1, 42) = 27.3, p < .001$, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) Gaze dispersion, (b) left mirror RT and (c) percentage of time spent looking at the left mirror

Fig. 3. Interaction effect between HMI and TOR time-budget conditions for the percentage of participants who checked at least one mirror before performing an action.

3.2 Driving behavior metrics

Participants in the “Eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI” condition presented increased TTC and reduced collision rate in comparison to the other conditions, $F(2,40) = 5.08$, $p = .011$ and $F(2,204) = 9.46$, $p < .001$, respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. (a) TTC and (b) collision rate in function of the HMI conditions

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to test the effectiveness of an eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI to improve SA reconstruction and thereby take-over performance and safety in more ecological settings, such as with a variety of use-cases and the driver being cognitively distracted. According to our results, the eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI improved: (i) SA reconstruction since participants presented higher gaze dispersion, faster RT to the left mirror and spent more time looking at the left mirror, which indicated more visual searches and more information gathered during the take-overs; (ii) take-over performance and safety with increased time to collision and fewer collisions.

Regarding limitations: In some cases, the differences between the two adaptive HMI conditions were not significant, which could arise from a lack of statistical power. We did not use a full factorial design; thus, we did not include a simple eye-gaze adaptive HMI due to time and sample constraints. We focused on the whole HMI, still it would be very interesting to add this condition for further analysis.

5. Conclusions

Our eye-gaze and situation adaptive HMI exhibited promising results with improved SA reconstruction and increased take-over performance and safety. Further analysis will focus on eye-gaze data with Markov analysis and physiological data. Overall, the adaptive HMIs seem to be a good option to ensure better take-over performance safety in comparison to non-adaptive HMIs.

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